

Multi Factor Security Model for IoT

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Abstract: Humans life is dependent on technology, if it is their health, travel, day to day life activities, living, moving, traveling, etc. technology is everywhere now and we cannot escape it. With all this, now there is an extra relief and support to human's daily life and work through the Internet of things. but, security issues and cyber-attacks are making the privacy of its users a challenging aspect of it, where the IoT device require and works on low power and memory, which makes it difficult to implement traditional cryptographic encryption and authentication algorithms which requires high computation power. Therefore, this research article is contributing to the existing works and literatures, by proposing and introducing a robust multi-factor authentication and security model for IoT called SAARZ which uses hardware-based Intrusion Prevention System using PUF, and also IDS technology for detecting unknown and known attacks couple with Hardware based IPS system using PUF, further it uses hash function, XOR operation, Timestamp, and Nonce. The informal analysis shows that, this Security Model is resilient against both known and unknown attacks.

Keywords: Multi Factor, Security Model, IoT, authentication, XOR, Hash function, Intrusion Detection System, Intrusion Prevention System, PUF, MAC address, CRP, Secret Key, Cryptography

1. Introduction

The term Internet of Things (IoT) was first introduced by Kevin Ashton in 1999, for supply chain management. As for today, the emerging technological advancements for connecting devices together using Internet for better management of human's daily life and businesses, where the IoT is being used in a large number of areas such as: health, transportation, smart cities, cars, manufacturing Industries, agriculture, and many more, where the data is collected by the sensors connected to different environments and are sent for analytics to different IoT platforms in the Internet and the results are shared with other devices or end users for better experience. According to Cisco, there is going to be 500 Billion devices connected to the Internet by 2030. While the security of these devices is still a big concern among different researchers. Due to the resource constrained nature of IoT devices considering memory and power, application of traditional cryptographic encryption and authentication mechanisms which requires huge computation power is not affordable and thus it is required to develop a lightweight mechanism for the IoT purpose, due to which lots of authentication schemes have been proposed since for years until now by different researchers in this field, but these protocols still lack some of the security measures required and are vulnerable to most of the attacks.

As the emerging technological advancements and innovations are on the spark, and our daily life dependency on these changes is also growing day by day, the same way vulnerabilities and cyber threats to these technologies are also increasing, for which at a government, business and personal level we need to be will assured of our data security from any type of illegitimate access or tampering.

Based on the review of multiple documents (journals, articles, books, conference papers, thesis, research papers) for this research article, which shows that, there still isn't any robust secure mechanism for keeping IoT devices secure from cyber-attacks. Hence,

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this paper proposes a multi-factor security model for IoT devices secure authentication, communication and threats detection and prevention mechanism, using secret keys, cryptographic hash function, XOR Operation, and also ΔT , timestamp, Nonce. Beside the aforementioned functions hardware-based IPS using PUF and network-based Intrusion Detection System is considered.

2. Related Works

Alizai et al [1] have proposed in their work that, for establishing a secure and reliable communication, a secure authentication approach between the IoT devices is required, which could be achieved through multi factor device authentication that encompasses both device capability and digital signature. They have mentioned that their proposed scheme would mitigate replay attack and man-in-the middle attack because of the nonce and timestamp factors. They have used Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) for the confidentiality. and have also included that the security issue still exists if the keys are stored in the devices, as the IoT devices could be stolen or compromised. However, Alsibahee et al [2] in their work have elaborated that, the proposed scheme [1] does not provide a mutual authentication mechanism to prevent illegal devices from stealing sensitive authentication parameters, and that the proposed scheme [1] is vulnerable to parallel session, forgery, brute force and dictionary attacks. Meanwhile Ahmad [16] has mentioned in his work that, the digital signature scheme [1] parameters are not adequate to claim authenticity.

Vinoth et al [3] have elaborated in their work that, because IoT devices are limited with computational and storage resources, due to which lightweight authentication schemes are proposed in order to reduce the computation, but these proposed schemes fail to support the required security or are unable to mitigate known attacks. And thus, they have proposed a multi-factor authenticated key agreement scheme which uses hash function, XOR operation and symmetric cryptography. And their proposed scheme is composed of offline sensing devices registration, user registration, login, authenticated key agreement, biometrics and password update, dynamically sensing devices joining phase and sensing devices revocation phase.

Ghani et al [4] have scrutinized and elaborated in their work that, the proposed protocol by Gope et al [5], is vulnerable to user traceability, stolen verifier, and denial of service attacks and therefore they have proposed an enhanced symmetric key-based authentication protocol for IoT, which counters these attacks and have been verified by ProVerif and BAN logic according to them. Their proposed protocol includes different phases like; user registration, anonymous authentication and key exchange phase, password update phase, new sensor node addition phase. But, Wang et al, [6] have mentioned in their work that proposed scheme [4] lacks and is vulnerable to diverse and serious security weaknesses as; user anonymity, efficient typo detection, desynchronization attack, forgery attack, replay attack, stolen verifier attack, session key disclosure attack.

Ming Jian et al [7] have proposed in their work an authentication protocol through self-identification method, in which mac address of the IoT device network component will be used to identify the IoT device and corresponding public key only once, where first the IoT device will broadcast its Mac address and based on that the service server will query it's information and public key from the manufacturer server of the device using Internet and during this process the IP address will be assigned to the device based on the specific time. Then the device will send its shared-key which is individually assigned to each IoT device by the manufacturer and will be protected by private key to the service server and finally encrypted data can be transferred in between.

R. Garg et al [8] have elaborated in their work that, due to the security and privacy vulnerabilities within the currently used centralized authentication system in IoT, Blockchain could be the best solution due to its decentralized working system and its security features in IoT three different layers (Application, Network and Perception layers) for preventing different existing attacks in each layer. But they have also concluded that due to the storage, processing power, time required for encryption algorithm requirements and scalability issues due to the size of Blockchain ledger are the problems that make this technology currently less suitable for IoT. As Wang et al [9] have illustrated in their work that, the application of blockchain in IoT faces problems such as computation, where the algorithms used in blockchain (zero-knowledge and ABE) are heavy for IoT devices, Storage problem, as the size of the blocks are large and without which the verification will not be possible and many more issues like this are existed, which makes it hard to be implemented.

Azroul et al [10] have proposed in their work an authentication protocol which includes four different phases (new sensor adding phase, user registration, login and authentication, and password changing phase). In the first phase gateway generates random ID and shared-key for the new sensor device and stores it on to the memory of device, in the next phase user can register itself through a secure channel (hash function algorithm), in the third phase communication is established between sensor, gateway and user through a public channel- for the user. the gateway compares the hash value received from the user with its computed hash value, for the sensor the gateway checks the correctness of sensor hash value. And mutually the user can authenticate the server by checking the validity of server hash value and the sensor also verifies the correctness of sensor hash value sent by the server. And according to their informal analysis this protocol is secure from password guessing attack, insider attack, replay attack, Denning-sacco attack, stolen verifier, DoS attack. They have used Scyther tool for formal security analysis of their protocol, which the results show that their protocol is much more secure than the previous protocol proposed by S.Kumari et al [11] according to their analysis.

El-hajj et al [12], have elaborate in their work, that because cryptographic schemes designed for main-powered, high processing and large memory devices do not suit the resource limited IoT devices, due to which lightweight authentication schemes has emerged. And they have mentioned that the main IoT security concerns are authentication, authorization, integrity, confidentiality, non-repudiation, availability, and privacy- for which mature lightweight cryptographic algorithms and security protocols is required.

Bendavid et al [13] have scrutinized in their work that, the proposed lightweight RFID mutual authentication protocol based on PUF by Xu et al [14] in their work, "a lightweight RFID mutual authentication protocol based on physical unclonable function, 2018" is vulnerable to desynchronization attack and to secret disclosure attack and hence suggested their own improved authentication protocol apart from PUF, it uses a cryptographic hash function as the core of security which includes two phases: the registration phase over a secure channel and the authentication phase over a public channel. However, Adeli et al [15] have elaborated in their work, that such authentication protocol cannot satisfy the IoT security protocol requirements.

Ahmed et al [16] have proposed in their work, a multifactor authentication mechanism that uses robust combiners of the hash functions which uses three secure keys for the sensor device- two private (one of these keys will be used for Geolocation of the Sensor) and one public- each IoT device has two secure keys- one private and one public, and they have mentioned that the user ID and Password authentication mechanism are the most

classical method for authentication techniques and are vulnerable method against eavesdropping or replay attacks. 144
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Ahmad [17] has proposed in his work, a secure symmetric cryptographic mechanism based on the certificate authority management and Elliptic Curve Diffie Hellman (ECDH) for securely exchanging the shared secret key to resolve spoofing attacks and preventing impersonation of certificate authority identify, and to share a digital certificate among Industrial IoT devices. He has further elaborated that symmetric and asymmetric cryptography cannot alone provide data integrity and sender authenticity. Hence, according to him a digital certificate must be used to associate an object's (sensor, actuator, user) identity to a public key using the digital signature of a trusted third party (Certificate Authority Center in this case), which will verify user's claim that the key belongs to him and prevent a spoofing attack. 146
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Chatterjee et al [18] have proposed in their work, a lightweight identity-based cryptosystem using PUF to generate public identity for each device as public key to encrypt the messages. But, Liu et al [19] have elaborated in their work that the proposed scheme [17] does not guarantee mutual authentication between two parties and is not resistant to modelling and eavesdropping attacks, and also it is vulnerable to impersonation attack as the CRPs are send as plaintext. As well due to the public key algorithm the protocol consumes more computation overhead. Hence, they have proposed a mutual-authenticated key distribution scheme [19] based on physical unclonable functions (PUFs) for dynamic sensor network which reduces the storage overhead and key exposure risks, it also provides mutual authentication by the PUF challenge-response mechanism which is not transmitted in plain form. Thakare et al [25], have mentioned in their work that the protocol [18] is vulnerable to guessing, embedded device impersonation, DoS, server impersonation, insider, database and cookie attacks. 156
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Choudhary et al [20] have proposed in their work, a mutual authentication and secret key exchange protocol (MAKE-IT) using hashing, ciphering, XOR, asymmetric and symmetric key cryptography and timestamps to overcome the deficiency of traditional authentication schemes. Their formal and informal analysis of the protocol (MAKE-IT) proves to be resistance against replay, modification, MITM, and impersonation attack according to them and Yan et al [21] in their work. Their protocol comprises of two stages: user device registration phase, and mutual authentication and secret key generation phase. According to M.li et al [22] in their work, the proposed scheme [20] provides secure mutual authentication and key exchange between different entities to limit unauthorized access. 169
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J.Meng et al [23] have proposed in their work, a lightweight mutual authentication protocol for IoT devices using hash functions, XOR and mainly based on PUFs, which provides higher security and reliability based on their formal analysis using improved BAN logic (by Mao and Body). They have considered reverse fuzzy extractor for avoiding noising PUFs and Their protocol is composed of three phases: the setup phase, the registration phase and the authentication phase. 178
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Q.Jiang et al [24] have proposed in their work, a scheme which uses PUF with the combination of password in Authentication and Key Agreement (AKA) protocol for securing IoV which is prone to physical attacks. And they have mentioned that their protocol is free from the influence of known attacks- they have adopted reverse fuzzy extractor to tolerate the noise of PUF response and to reduce the computational burden on user devices and sensor, and their protocol is composed of three phases: system setup phase, registration phase, login and authentication phase. According to J. Meng et al [23] the proposed scheme [24] overhead is increased resulting from the asymmetric cryptography. 184
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Thakare et al [25] have introduced in their work, an authentication scheme using hash function, concatenation and XOR, ECDLP and CDHP, their scheme is composed of two phases: registration phase and the password-authentication phase which includes the session key distribution step. They have claimed that the protocol is preventive against all kinds of active and passive attacks.

Gope et al [33] have proposed in their work, a lightweight and privacy preserving mutual user authentication protocol. And they have considered the physical layer security of the sensor nodes using lightweight cryptographic primitives such as; one-way hash function, physically unclonable function (PUF) and bitwise exclusive (XOR) operators. Their scheme comprises of four phases: user registration phase, sensor node registration phase, authentication phase, and physical temper checking, and secure periodical data collection phase. According to Choudhry et al [20], this protocol can reduce the active lifetime of the devices and network because of its large-sized messages during the authentication and key exchange phase.

3. Proposed IoT Security Model

a multi-factor IoT security model which comprises of both authentication mechanism using different cryptographic techniques, and as well the threats detection and prevention system is considered to act as an extra line of defense or security in IoT technology environment

3.1. Research contribution

- The proposed security model uses lightweight cryptographic techniques as; hash function, XOR operation and symmetric cryptography, which is suitable for the resource constrained IoT devices.
- In this model PUF is considered for device authentication purpose, due to which the security of the proposed model against impersonation and physical tampering is high.
- The proposed model uses IoT devices MAC address and for the Gateway both the MAC address and IP address as the ID, for better authorization and identification purpose.
- Timestamp, Nonce, and allowable transmission delay has been used to protect the IoT devices data transmission from replay and modification attack.
- For better security and authentication support, specification-based Intrusion Detection System is considered, which will detect both known and unknown attacks.

3.2. Requirement Elicitation Technique

The researcher has used scenario and documents review and analysis elicitation technique. Where in scenario part the stepwise execution of involved processes in the system for security implementation in IoT and its behavior is explained. And because it is recommended that beside with scenario elicitation technique another requirement elicitation technique must be used, for which the researcher has considered and used documents review and analysis technique where researcher has reviewed a large number of documents (research papers, journals, books, conference papers).

3.3. Network Diagram

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Figure 1. Network Diagram

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- Gateway:** Gateway provides the interface to user for getting connected to the IoT network. the gateway forwards the received data from the sensor nodes and forward them to the cloud-based analysis system and for the authentication of devices purpose. before the data could be received, the gateway-node needs to check the legitimacy of the sensor node. On the other hand, a user might want to access data from a specific sensor node directly, like in the healthcare environment a doctor might need to access the patient related data directly, before all this happens still the gateway needs to authenticate the device. Gateway node in this project is considered to be a resourceful device in regard to the computation and memory power.
- IoT nodes:** a set of sensor nodes are deployed on the field or some environment for monitoring or doing some specific processes. Sensor nodes collect data from their surrounding environment using the sensors and further send them to the gateway to be transferred into the cloud for analysis and further decision-making purpose.
- IDS Sensor:** for network traffic analysis IDS Sensors are deployed at each subnet of the network topology, which will analyze the network traffic and will keep its record, as well it will be generating alerts to the admin in case of any threat detection or abnormal activity of the network traffic. The collected data by the IDS Sensors, is sent to the cloud for the experts' analytics process.

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- *Authentication Server*: the AS will have the PUF CRP records Database, secret keys of the devices, it will generate keys for new devices which will be registered and then deployed to IoT environment and will keep the records of the new devices PUF CRPs for future IoT devices authentication and authorization purpose, prior to the deployment.
- *ASA Firewall*: this will provide secure private channel for the IoT data transmission between the gateway node and the IoT main servers site. Through the private channel (secure channel) the authentication and data access process between the remote Main office will happen, where the IDS management system and Authentication server resides. And using the public channel, remote users will be able to get access to the IoT devices from remote location. The connection will be secured using VPN, and Access Lists must be configured for only allowing traffic from specific hosts.

3.4. Intrusion Prevention System

Researcher has considered hardware-based intrusion prevention system using PUF, where no device will be able to authenticate itself and get access to the IoT network due to the uniqueness of the PUF, which is called and considered as the digital fingerprints of a device. So, if any intruder or adversary wants to get access to the IoT network and want to have access to IoT devices data, will not be able to do it, as it is difficult to clone the same PUF embedded into the IoT devices, because during the manufacturing process specific variations and unique computation characteristics are manufactured with the PUFs. And Due to the variations manufactured, completely un-identical CRPs for each PUF are produced. So, using this physical characteristic of a device which is also called digital fingerprints, intrusion prevention will be made possible.

3.5. Intrusion Detection System

As IDS is threat detection system which is of three types: signature based (misuse), anomaly based and specification-based intrusion detection systems. In signature based previously known attacks signatures or patterns are considered and based on the detection of any known attacks, alert will be generated and its drawback is that it cannot detect novel and unknown attacks, while in anomaly-based IDS new and previously unknown attacks detection is possible where Machine Learning and Deep Learning technique is used for capturing normal system behavior and its drawback is that it generates high rate of false alarms because of previously unknown network behavior though which might be legitimate in reality, on the other hand specification-based is similar to anomaly-based IDS but in here an expert person will be creating rules and will mark specific traffic as normal instead of Machine and Deep Learning technique and it has the strengths of both misuse and anomaly-based IDS systems. In this project the researcher has considered specification-based IDS system through distributed deployment rather than centralized deployment, in order to reduce the communication overhead.

- *IDS Management Server*: the management server for Intrusion Detection System resides at the main office or cloud of the IoT network, and this Server will be analyzing the data received through the IDS Sensors, for further rules generation.
- *IDS Sensor*: the sensors of the Intrusion Detection System (IDS) will be monitoring the network traffic of specified subnet and will be sending the captured network traffic back to the IDS Management Server, and will also be generating alerts for any intrusion and network traffic abnormality, by comparing the network traffic with previously recorded normal behavior and patterns of the network traffic.

4. Proposed IoT Security Authentication Model

Proposed secure IoT devices authentication model which is physically secured by using PUF function, also the PUF is considered to work as Intrusion Prevention based on hardware characteristics of an IoT device, meanwhile encryption and security mechanisms such as hash function, private key, exclusive OR (XOR) operation, nonce, MAC address of device, timestamp, and allowable transmission delay are used. The proposed authentication protocol will work as under:

4.1. Device Registration Phase:

Prior to any deployment of IoT devices to the field or to the relevant IoT Wireless Sensor Network (WSN), each device will be embedded with PUF ICs and a Challenge Response Pairs (CRPs) of the PUF will be recorded into the database of Authentication Server. A Secret key will be stored into the IoT device for encryption and decryption of the messages exchanged by the entities and the devices will be programmed to perform cryptographic functions and operations (XOR and Hash). The IoT devices will also be equipped with a MAC address and IP.

4.2. Authentication Phase:

when a device wants to connect to the IoT network for accessing data or services offered by the network using IoT WSN, the request will be sent to the Gateway node and gateway node will decrypt the message and calculate $ID_d = TID_d \oplus N_d$ to find the MAC address and will then check its mac address table to make sure that the requested IoT device mac address is registered; if the mac address is registered then the Gateway node will forward the request to the Authentication Server, during this connection first the gateway will be authenticated by the Authentication Server. The authentication of IoT devices will happen through the secure / private channel between the Gateway and Authentication Server and the request of the new IoT devices will be received through the insecure / public channel. The authentication process is illustrated as under:

- The IoT devices are equipped with pre-shared Secret Key, MAC address, Physical Unclonable Function IC, and programmed to perform specific cryptographic operation and functions.
- The new device will send a request to the Gateway Node (GWn) for accessing the network and the IoT resources. Where the device will first generate N_d and compute a Temporary ID $(TID_d = ID_d \oplus N_d)$, the device will perform hash function and will encrypt the message with the shared secret key between the Device and the Gateway node (k_{dg}).
- The gateway node will check the freshness of the message using the Timestamp, and will find the MAC address of the IoT device ($ID_d = TID_d \oplus N_d$) once the MAC address is found, then the Gateway node will check its registered MAC address table for that specific device.
- If the mac address is registered, the Gateway node will assign an IP address to the IoT device at first and meanwhile will forward the request to the Authentication Server for further authentication process.
- The Gateway node will generate a new message which will carry the original request message sent by the IoT device. Where the Gateway node will choose a

Temporary ID ($TID_g = ID_g \boxplus N_g$) using its MAC address and IP address. 346
 And will generate a N_g -using the nonce the Gateway node will perform XOR op- 347
 eration on the message of IoT device, and will then perform hash function. At the 348
 end the Gateway node will encrypt the message using the pre-shared key between 349
 the Gateway node and the Authentication server, and will send the message to 350
 AS. 351

- The AS by the time receives the message, will check its freshness and will also 352
 check the ID of Gateway node ($ID_g = TID_g \ominus N_g$) and will verify the hash func- 353
 tion. If the ID, hash and pre-shared secret key is correct, the AS for further au- 354
 thentication will send a challenge to the Gateway node. 355
- AS based on the specifications provided by the Gateway for its identity, will select 356
 a random CRP and will generate a new nonce N_{AS} , using the nonce the AS will 357
 perform XOR operation on the Challenge; will perform hash-function and also 358
 encrypt the message with the pre-shared secret key between the Gateway node 359
 and AS. And will send the challenge to the Gateway node. 360
- As the message is received by the Gateway node, GW will check its freshness and 361
 will verify the hash. Further, GW will derive the challenge as $C_g = f_{AS_1} \ominus N_{AS}$, 362
 and using its PUF the GW node will output or generate the response for the given 363
 challenge. Now, the Gateway node will generate a new nonce and will then per- 364
 form XOR operation on the Response using the nonce; will perform hash-function 365
 and will finally encrypt the message using the pre-shared secret key between the 366
 gateway node and AS. The encrypted response message will be sent to AS. 367
- As the response message is received by the AS, the allowable transmission delay 368
 $|T_{AS} - T_g| \leq \Delta T$ and timestamp will be checked for freshness of the message. 369
 Then the hash will be verified for the message integrity; the AS server will derive 370
 the response for the challenge given ($R_g = f_{g_2} \ominus N_g$) 371
- The AS will check its previously random challenge CRP record table and will ver- 372
 ify the response against the given challenge. And if the response is correct, then 373
 the gateway node is successfully authenticated. 374

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DV	GW	AS
<p>Generate: N_d Computes: $TID_d = ID_d \oplus N_d$ $h_{d_1}(\cdot) = h(TID_d \ N_d \ K_{DAs})$ $ID_d = mac_d \oplus r$ M_{d_1} $= k_{d_g}(TID_d, N_d, h_{d_1}(\cdot), T_d, K_{DAs})$</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin-top: 10px;"> $M_{d_1} = k_{d_g}(TID_d, N_d, h_{d_1}(\cdot), T_d, K_{DAs})$ </div>	<p>Will check the message for freshness using the Timestamp computes: $ID_d = TID_d \oplus N_d$ if the mac address (ID) is correct, gateway will forward the message to AS</p>	
	<p>$ID_g = (mac_g \ IP_g) \oplus r$ Verify: $h_{d_1}(\cdot)$ Generate: N_g Computes: $TID_g = ID_g \oplus N_g$ $f_{g_1} = M_{d_1} \oplus N_g$ $h(\cdot) = h(f_{g_1} \ N_g \ TID_g)$ $M_{g_1} = K_{GA}(TID_g, f_{g_1}, h(\cdot), T_g)$</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin-top: 10px;"> $M_{g_1} = K_{GA}(TID_g, f_{g_1}, h(\cdot), T_g)$ </div>	<p>The AS will check the freshness of the message using the Timestamp, if correct: Check: $ID_g = TID_g \oplus N_g$ Verify: $h(\cdot)$ If the ID of GW is correct:</p>
		<p>If the ID of GW is correct: Select: (C_g, R_g) Generate: N_{As} $f_{As_1} = C_g \oplus N_{As}$ $h(\cdot) = h(f_{As_1} \ C_g \ N_{As})$ M_{As_1} $= K_{GA}(f_{As_1}, h(\cdot), N_{As}, T_{As})$</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin-top: 10px;"> $M_{As_1} = K_{GA}(f_{As_1}, h(\cdot), N_{As}, T_{As})$ </div>
	<p>Check freshness of message Verify: $h(\cdot)$ Generate: N_g Derive: $C_g = f_{As_1} \oplus N_{As}$ Compute: $R_g = P_g(C_g)$ $f_{g_2} = R_g \oplus N_g$ Compute: $h(\cdot) =$ $h(f_{g_2} \ TID_g \ N_g)$ $M_{g_2} = K_{GAs}(TID_g, f_{g_2}, N_g, T_g)$</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin-top: 10px;"> $M_{g_2} = K_{GAs}(TID_g, f_{g_2}, N_g, T_g)$ </div>	<p>Compute: $T_{As} - T_g \leq \Delta T$ Check freshness of message Verify: $h(\cdot)$ Derive: $R_g = f_{g_2} \oplus N_g$ If correct: The Gateway request message for authenticating the IoT device will be checked.</p>

After the Gateway node is authenticated by the Authentication server, now the Authentication Server will generate a new Challenge for the authentication of the Device, which has requested to get access or connect to IoT network or maybe to access another IoT Sensor Node data. But before that to happen, the previously sent request message of IoT device which is sent by the Gateway will be checked and decrypted, As illustrated under:

- The AS will decrypt the message using the pre-shared secret key between the Gateway node and the Authentication server.
- The hash function and the pre-shared secret key between the AS and the IoT device will be verified by the Authentication server, and then the AS will decrypt the IoT device message by performing XOR operation using the nonce of the gateway ($M_{d_1} = f_{g_1} \otimes N_g$), and will then check the ID of IoT device as: $ID_d = TID_d \boxtimes N_d$. If the IoT device ID and pre-shared secret key is verified, then the AS will randomly select a CRP for the specific device from its database of CRP records.
- The AS will select a CRP; generate a random nonce N_{As} , and will perform XOR operation on the Challenge to be sent using the nonce. Then the AS will perform its hash function and will encrypt the challenge message using the pre-shared secret key between the AS and the IoT device. Finally, the challenge message will be sent to the gateway node to be forwarded to the IoT device, which has requested to join or gain access to the IoT network resources.
- The GWn will check the freshness of the message using the Timestamp and the allowable transmission delay threshold (ΔT). if the parameters are correct the Gateway node will forward the message to the IoT by encrypting it using the pre-shared key between the IoT device and the Gateway node.
- As the target device must already have PUF, and should be programmed to perform the relevant required cryptographic functions and operations.
- The IoT device will check the freshness of the message and the transmission delay (ΔT). and will decrypt the message using the pre-shared key between the Gateway node and IoT device; will verify the hash function and derive the challenge given by the Authentication server ($C_d = f_{As_2} \otimes N_{As}$); the IoT device will compute the challenge for response using its PUF and will generate a new nonce. Using the nonce the IoT device will perform XOR operation on the response and encrypt it using the pre-shared key between the AS and the IoT device; will also perform hash function. Then the message will be encrypted by the IoT device using its pre-shared key with the Gateway node. Finally, the encrypted response message will be sent to Gateway node to be forwarded to the AS.
- The GWn will check the freshness of the message using the timestamp and transmission delay threshold. And will also verify the ID of the IoT device ($(ID_d = TID_d \boxtimes N_d)$), if the parameters are correct the gateway node will forward the message to AS.
- the Gateway node will generate a new nonce, and will perform XOR operation on the message M_{d_2} ; Gateway node will also perform its hash

function and will finally encrypt the message using its pre-shared secret key with the AS, which will be containing the response message of the IoT device.

- The AS will check the freshness of the message using timestamp and allowable transmission delay threshold and will verify the hash function. The ID for the Gateway node will be verified using its TID ($ID_g = TID_g \otimes N_g$). If the parameters are correct the AS will decrypt the message and will check if the response is correct. In case the response is correct the IoT device is successfully authenticated.

DV	GW	AS
		<p>Decrypt: using K_{GAS}</p> <p>Verify: K_{DAS}</p> <p>Verify: $h_{d_1}(\cdot)$</p> <p>Compute: $M_{d_1} = f_{g_1} \oplus N_g$</p> <p>Check: $ID_d = TID_d \oplus N_d$</p> <p>If the device ID and Secret key is correct, the AS server will further send a challenge based on identifications the device has sent</p>
		<p>Select: (C_d, R_d)</p> <p>Generate: N_{AS}</p> <p>$f_{AS_2} = C_d \oplus N_{AS}$</p> <p>$h(\cdot) = h(f_{AS_2} \parallel C_d \parallel N_{AS})$</p> <p>$M_{AS_2}$ $= K_{DAS}(f_{AS_2}, h(\cdot), N_{AS}, T_{AS})$</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: 10px auto;"> $M_{AS_2} = K_{DAS}(f_{AS_2}, h(\cdot), N_{AS}, T_{AS})$ </div>
	<p>Check freshness of the message</p> <p>$T_g - T_{AS} \leq \Delta T$</p> <p>Verify: $h(\cdot)$</p>	

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Notation	Description
K_{GAS}	Secret key of GW and AS
K_{DAS}	Secret key of IoT DV and AS
TID_i	Temporary ID
ID_i	ID
P_i	Physical unclonable function
M_i	message
DV	Device
GW	Gateway node
AS	Authentication server
h	Hash function
\oplus	Exclusive OR operation
C_i	Challenge
\parallel	Concatenation
N_i	Nonce
ΔT	Allowable transmission delay
R_i	response
T_i	Times stamp
r	Random number
IP_i	IP Address

5. proposed IDS Model

To improve the security efficiency in the proposed security model for IoT, which comprises of hardware-based Intrusion prevention system using PUF, authentication using cryptographic functions and operations, specification-based along with misuse intrusion detection system is considered as another line of defense for IoT protection against cyber-attacks, as signature-based (misuse) IDS detection rate for known attacks is higher while in specification-based IDS, detection rate of new and unknown attacks is higher, where IoT devices and normal network traffic and behavior is captured to learn normal patterns for the network traffic, and if any abnormal behavior outside the specified threshold or the learned normal patterns is captured will be labeled as anomalous. So, it is good to have them both at different detection processes. In the proposed model, IDS sensors are deployed at each subnet of the network and is responsible for the monitoring of the traffic on that specific subnet, in order to minimize the communication overhead of the network traffic. Each sensor node will be analyzing the network traffic of related subnet and will compare it to the previously recorded normal network activity threshold during a specific time period. If abnormal network activity is detected it will consider it as intrusion and will label the packet as intrusion, will block the source and drop the packet, meanwhile

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an alert will be generated of intrusion detection by the relevant IDS Sensor of the subnet and will be sent to the IDS management server on the cloud or the main site for analysis purpose, the admin or system expert will analyze the alert and will try to find its origination, if the device was intruder the Admin will create a new rule on the IDS system (management server) and update the database rules for the new attack.

In case an authentication process is unsuccessful or the Gateway node or Authentication server rejects a request, that transmission will be considered as intrusion and will be forwarded by the GW node. As for the IoT Devices in the perception layers are resource constrained, due to which the implementation of both IDS modules (specification-based and misuse-based) will not be feasible because of the traffic generated by this type of system. Hence, the researcher has considered only the statistical module of specification-based IDS system on that subnet, where only the normal traffic will be monitored by the IDS Sensor.

6. 4. Informal Analysis of The Proposed Security Model

based on the security parameters considered for devices security in IoT environment, the proposed model is resilient against the known and un-known attacks, as beside the secure authentication mechanism using PUF and other cryptographic techniques, the specification-based IDS system is also considered which will not only detect all known attacks but will be able to detect new attacks as will using the normal patterns of the network traffic previously specified.

4. Discussion

As in the introduction and for this research article the objectives were; to design a robust security model for secure authentication in the IoT technology, resilience of the designed security model against the all known and novel attacks in IoT technology, and designing an extra layer of security coupled with the authentication mechanism, to be able to achieve the second objective. Meanwhile the main goal and aim of this project was to introduce and design a robust IoT security model for securing the IoT environment against cyber-attacks and to ensure data Integrity, confidentiality, authenticity and non-repudiation in the IoT environment.

As for the objectives and Goal of this project are considered, this paper has achieved them all. As, a robust authentication security model which uses PUF along with other lightweight cryptographic operations and functions like; XOR operation, hash function and encryption using secret keys, and also it uses nonce and timestamp for ensuring message or data integrity and freshness, which ensures that the Adversary will not be able to replay or alter the message. Meanwhile, the proposed security model is able to perform Intrusion Prevention based on hardware characteristics of the IoT devices (PUF) and rule-based as well misuse modules integrated with Intrusion Detection using the misuse and specification-based IDS Systems.

IoT technology is going to be the leading technology on which humans will be more dependent around the world, where we all would need or come to use it at every single moment or step of our daily life activities, in order to be able to get things done more easily and automatically either from close or remote location. there still isn't specific IoT technology based standard authentication and communication protocols, which could be accepted and used like the protocols and models used in the traditional networks and technologies. And there is still lots of researches and developments undergoing and required among the researchers and technological institutions for developing specific protocols to be used in this technology, where heterogenous devices forms its infrastructure and core.

The resource limited aspect of this technology, related to communication and computation power also storage limitation has made it more attractive for both those whom

are willing to harm and to have illegitimate access to the device in IoT and as well to the technological institutions, other entities and researchers in order to come up with better security options considering the communication, authentication and detection protocols along with new technological devices specific to the IoT technology. As for example; the TCP/IP model is not suitable for this technology due to the large number of protocols in each layer as well the security issues in it and also the large header size of packets, where even there isn't need to have them tagged in to a message of IoT.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not Applicable

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